

Effect of Firm Attributes on Financial Reporting Timeliness of Listed Firms on the Nigeria Stock Exchange

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Abstract

The issue of audit timeliness is central to quality of financial report and equally influence the decisions of investors on where to commit their resources. While there is a regulatory requirement on when financial reports should be made available, it appears that firms have continued to flout the requirements of the regulations. Considering the fact that investors eagerly anticipate the release of financial report to invest in a firm, a delay in such report could lead to investment in an alternate firm. It is against this backdrop that this study examine the effect of selected firm's attributes on financial reporting timeliness of listed firms in Nigeria. The study used a sample of 65 firms out of the total population of 189 listed firms on the Nigeria stock exchange. The data were collected from the annual financial statement of the firms and were analysed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses were tested using Poisson regression analysis technique. The result shows that firm characteristics are significant determinants of financial reporting timeliness. Based on the finding, the study recommends that as firms grow in size the need to have automated system of preparing financial reports becomes eminent. This will do away with size effect were it will take longer time for large firms to prepare their financial reports due to many branches and complicated business dealings. Thus, though the aggregate firm's result shows a decreasing reporting delay with increase in size, the SEC should be mindful of the other sectors these (Firms in the Agricultural, conglomerate and insurance sectors) were increasing size increases delay. It is also recommended that non-profitable and leveraged firms should still try to present their financial reports timely since some investors also takes into consideration future profit prospects and not just the current profit in other to invest in a firm.

Keywords: Firm attributes, reporting timeliness and Poisson regression

1.1 Introduction

One of the important objectives of corporate reporting is to provide information that will assist both internal and external users in decision making. This information, however, is required to be made available within a short period of time from the end of the reported period otherwise such accounting information may lose its economic value. This is where timeliness comes in. The issue of timeliness involves and demands that the management of the company who prepares the reports and the auditor who provides the audit and assurance services must both be thoughtful about timeliness. For instance, reducing audit delays in a manner to enhancing and addressing the timeliness of audit reports is considered a very crucial issue in accounting profession in general; and specifically to the users of accounting information, regulatory and professional bodies.

Timely presentation of financial reports affects the decision making process of investors and other users. Lack of timely information could make the investors to seek for alternative sources of information. Consequently, this may affect the investment opportunity decision of the organization as rightly pointed out by Bamber, Bamber and Schoderbek (1993:29) that: "delayed disclosure of financial information may encourage certain corrupt investors to acquire costly private pre-disclosure information and thus exploiting their private information at the expense of the 'less informed' investors".

A major problem identified in literature is that previous studies relied only on ordinary least square regression model which as noted in Lee and Jahng (2008), Guilherme, João and Paulo (2012) is not suitable for a count dependent variable. Thus this study is using Poission regression model which is most appropriate for the analysis. Also, previous studies have also focused only on one sector, however, this study is considering all firms listed in the stock market. The remaining part of this study focuses on literature review, methodology, results, conclusion and recommendation.

2.0 Literature Review

Owusu-Ansah (2000) investigates empirically the timeliness of annual reporting by 47 non- financial companies listed on the Zimbabwe Stock Exchange. From the investigations, the study finds firm size, profitability and firm age to exhibit a significant impact on financial reporting timeliness. In addition, the results indicated that audit reporting lead time is significantly associated with the timeliness with which sample companies release their preliminary annual earnings announcements, but not with the timeliness of the audited annual reports. The study finding is relevant to Zimbabwe while this

current study used panel regression analysis and it cannot be used in Nigeria because of its environment.

Dogan, Coskun and Celik(2007) examines the relationship between a set of explanatory variables (such as good or bad news, financial risk, size and industry) and the timing of annual reports released in companies listed on the Istanbul Stock Exchange (ISE). The study applied OLS regression analysis and found that timeliness in reporting by ISE listed companies is influenced by their profitability. Good news firms (measured by ROE and ROA) release their annual reports earlier than bad news firms do. The study also found that the timing of annual report releases is affected significantly by company size, increased financial risk, and the timing policy of previous years. The study uses OLS regression analysis and the finding is relevant to Istanbul while this current study used panel regression analysis and it cannot be used in Nigeria because of its environment.

Moradi and Hoseini (2009) examines the association between size, age, debt- equity ratio, profitability, audit opinion and audit delay. The sample comprises Production Company listed in Tehran stock Exchange during the period 1977-1985. The study applied OLS regression analysis and the result of testing the hypotheses of the study proves to be significantly associated between Audit delay and size, age, debt- equity ratio, profitability and audit opinion. The study used OLS regression analysis while this current study used panel regression analysis.

In China, McGee and Yuan (2008a) evaluates financial reporting timeliness. The study scaled timeliness by totalling the number of days that passed by flanked by year-end and independent auditors report date for several Chinese firms. Subsequently, a comparison was made with those of non-Chinese firms in developed market economies to ascertain the existence of a significant difference. The study uses correlation regression analysis also examines which independent audit firms issued the audit opinion and which sets of accounting standards were used (IFRS, US GAAP or Chinese accounting standards) to determine which audit firms and accounting standards tend to dominate. The study uses correlation regression analysis and the finding is relevant to China while this current study uses Poisson panel regression analysis and it cannot be used in Nigeria because of its environment.

McGee and Yuan (2008b) assesses for the timeliness of financial reporting in several transition economies that are new European Union members and makes comparisons to companies in four older members of the EU. The goal of the study was to determine whether there is a significant difference in the timeliness of financial reporting between the two groups of companies. The study finds that companies in the new EU member states issue their financial

information in a fashion that is just as timely as that of companies in the old EU. The study finding is restricted to old Europe.

Conover, Miller and Szakmary (2008) examines financial reporting lags, the incidence of late filing, and the relationship between reporting lags, firm performance and the degree of capital market scrutiny. Their major focus was to find out whether the incidence of late filing, and the relationship between reporting days and other variables, differs systematically between common law and code law countries. The study finds that timely filing is less frequent in code law countries. Also, the study asserts a connection between common law countries and Poor organisation performance, and stretched reporting lag. The study additionally found that though more prominent capital market examination and timelier filing are connected, there is less confirmation for a connection between the level of debt financing and timely filing in code law nations. The study stopped in 2008 while this study extends to 2017.

Al-Ajmi (2008) investigates the timeliness of annual reports of an unbalanced panel of 231 firms-years of financial and non- financial companies listed on the Bahrain Stock Exchange. The primary objective of the investigation was to ascertain the determinants of the timeliness of Bahraini annual reports spanning a duration of 1999-2006. The study established that organisation's size, profitability, and leverage are key contributing factor. While the impact of accounting complexity or auditor type (Big Four or non-Big Four) were not confirmed. Also, the documented that corporate governance proxies were found to be a strong determining factor within the period between the auditors' signature dates and the publication dates. The study employed OLS regression analysis and the period of the study is old, therefore there is need to extend the study period to 2017 and this study used panel Poisson regression analysis.

Dardor (2009) studies the determinants and extent of reporting delay in 33 firms over a period of two years. The study found that it takes an average of 154.86 days lag for making public audit reports. It was further established from the OLS regression estimation that firm size, profitability, firm age, number of accountants, proficiency of accountants, and audit opinion has a significant impact on publishing delay. Nonetheless, the study found no association with the type of accounting system and publishing delay. The study employed OLS regression analysis while this current study used panel Poisson regression analysis.

Aubert (2009) empirically investigated how French listed companies decide when to announce their corporate annual earnings (parent company and consolidated company) as well as the full sets of (non) audited financial reports. The aim of the study was to investigate whether firms facing losses versus profit, good news versus bad news, exhibiting excessive stock price volatility

(risk), fluctuating trade volumes, past economic performance, market pressure, accounting complexity or earnings management issues (expressed as discretionary accruals) may choose to influence DELAY1 and DELAY2 variables. As a result, R-squared figures for the regressions ranged from about 27 to 44%, indicating that, on average, the variables tested explained a large proportion of the cross-sectional variability in DELAY ½ reporting lags. In addition to these results, non-tabulated descriptive statistics indicate that SBF 250 firms publish their financial reports an average 116.07 days after the fiscal year-end ($\sigma = 35$ days). This means that most French publicly-traded companies would need to reduce their reporting lags to comply with prescribed guidelines and thus achieve acceptable transparency performance. The finding of the study is restricted to France.

3.0 Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the ex-post facto research design. The choice of the design is anchored on the premises that the event of study has already taken place. The population of the study is the 189 firms listed on the floor of the Nigeria stock exchange. Out of the total of the population sixty five firms were selected as a sample across all the industries in the market. The study arrived at the selected sample after removing all firms that were listed after year 2007. Also, firms with inconsistency in financial reporting were also excluded from the sample selection. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistic, and the hypotheses tested using Poisson regression analysis. The use of Poisson regression is based on the fact that the dependent variable in the study is a count data (number of days). The regression model is presented below.

The Poisson regression model is based on the assumption that the dependent variable follow a Poisson distribution which is usually obtained from a count data. In this study, the dependent variable is financial reporting timeliness which Audit Delay (AD) and it represent number of days it takes for financial report to be reported. AD is said to have a Poisson distribution that takes integer values of $AD = 0,1,2,3, \dots$

The general model is The Poisson distribution function can be expressed in the form:

$$f(AD) = \frac{\mu^{AD} e^{-\mu}}{AD!} \text{ where } AD = 0,1,2, \dots N$$

Where $f(AD)$ denotes the probability that the variable Audit Delay AD takes non-negative interger values and $AD!$ Stands for $AD! = AD \times (AD - 1) \times (AD - 2) \times \dots \times 1$.

As noted in Gujarati and Porter (2009) it can be proved that:

$$E(AD) = \mu \quad 1$$

$$var(Y) = \mu \quad 2$$

This proves that the variance of a Poisson distribution is equal to its mean

The general form of the regression model takes the form

$$AD_i = E(AD) + \mu_i \quad 3$$

Since $E(AD)$ in model 1 is the same as μ it then implies that model 3 can be expressed as:

$$AD_i = E(AD_i) + \mu_i = \mu_i + \mu_i \quad 4$$

The dependent variable AD is independently distributed as Poisson random variable with mean μ_i for each individual expressed as:

$$\mu_i = E(AD_i) = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \dots + \beta_n X_{nit} \quad 5$$

From the general form of the model in model 5, the various models for the test of various hypotheses are presented below:

$$E(AD_{it}) = \alpha + \beta_1 FS_{it} + \beta_2 EPS_{2it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} \quad 6$$

Where: AD = Audit Delay, FS = Firm Size, EPS = Profitability, LEV = Leverage

4.0 Results and Discussion

The data collected for this study are with respect to financial reporting delay, firm size, profitability and leverage are presented in this section of the study.

Table 4.1.: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
AD	715	94.20	37.41	17.00	343.00
FS	715	8.56	1.91	4.00	12.00
EPS	712	8.59	39.65	-478.33	413.06
LEV	715	2.85	9.16	7.22	191.21

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables in the study. The result shows that on average it takes around 94 days (three months) from the statutory requirement day of 31st December for the firms to submit their financial reports. The minimum period is 17 days which implies that no firm was able to meet the deadline of 31st December. On the other hand the maximum period is 343 day which is very high. This implies that it takes some firms almost a year after the deadline to file their financial reports. The average delay is higher in the consumer goods section of the listed firms (See Table A4 in the Appendix) with a mean value of 113 days delay followed by the Oil and Gas sector with a mean of 106 days. These two sectors have diverse business operation and complicated transactions which cause the substantial delays in their financial reporting. The

average value of profitability of the firms is 8.59 with a deviation from profitability being 39.65 which is very high due to a high level of loss incurred by a firm in the group and another extreme maximum value of 413.06. The average value of leverage is 2.85 with a minimum of 7.22, the variable has relatively normal volatility as shown by the standard deviation value of 9.16.

4.2 Firm Attributes as Determinant of Financial Reporting Timeliness of Listed Firms

VARIABLES	(TOI) Ad	(IND) Ad	(CON) Ad	(BNK) Ad	(COM) Ad	(AGC) Ad	(OG) ad	(INS) ad
Fscs	-0.0112* (0.00605)	-0.0311* (0.0171)	-0.357*** (0.0305)	-0.00343 (0.0128)	0.0445*** (0.0122)	0.0109 (0.0165)	-0.0907*** (0.0344)	0.0943*** (0.0161)
Eps	-0.000611*** (0.000104)	-0.00141 (0.000958)	-0.000167 (0.000138)	0.000283 (0.000334)	-0.00413*** (0.000369)	0.000136 (0.00146)	-0.00120*** (0.000299)	0.00181** (0.000859)
Lev	0.00243*** (0.000392)	0.00417 (0.0123)	0.000810 (0.000827)	0.00326*** (0.000447)	-0.113*** (0.0127)	0.0179** (0.00771)	-0.0192*** (0.00638)	-0.0158* (0.00853)
Constant ad	4.639*** (0.0593)	4.658*** (0.132)	7.998*** (0.334)	4.437*** (0.143)	4.737*** (0.166)	4.381*** (0.123)	5.450*** (0.284)	3.671*** (0.162)
Constant lnalpha	-2.952*** (0.177)	-2.964*** (0.404)	-2.122*** (0.638)	-3.918*** (0.439)	-1.946*** (0.528)	-8.077*** (2.757)	-2.774*** (0.507)	-3.390*** (0.390)
Observations	712	143	52	142	77	55	88	154
Number of id	65	13	5	13	7	5	8	14

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 4.2 shows the result of some corporate attributes and how they affect audit delay of listed firms in the Nigeria stock exchange. Again, the results are presented with respect to the various sectors and the aggregate of all the listed firms. The corporate attributes considered in here are the firm size, earnings per share and leverage.

The result in the second column is with respect to the industrial goods sector. The result shows that when the corporate attributes variables are not being considered the level of audit delay of the firms grows at a constant value of 4.658 with statistical significance. When variable like firm size is considered, the result shows that a percentage change in firm size leads to a decrease of 0.0311 in audit delay. The result has no statistical significance at 5%. Also, considering the variable earnings per share, the result shows that a unit increase in the value of profitability will lead to a 0.00141 decrease in the number of days audit report is delayed. The result also has no statistical significance. Lastly for the industrial goods industrial, the result with respect to leverage shows that a unit increase in the value of leverage will lead to a 0.00417 increase in the numbers of days financial reports are delayed. Again, the result does not have statistical significance. The general result is that even though two of the variables were able to reduce the number of the days financial reports are delayed, all the variables have no statistical significance.

The third column shows the result with respect to conglomerates. The result shows that the value of constant is 7.988 which has statistical significance value at both 1% and 5% respectively. Considering each of the variables in the model the result shows that, a percentage increase in the value of firm size will lead to a 0.357 decrease in audit delay. The result is significant at 1% and 5% respectively. The result for profitability also shows a negative coefficient of -0.000167 which implies that a unit increase in the level of profitability of the firms will lead to a 0.000167 delay in financial report, however, the result has no statistical significance. With respect to leverage the result for the conglomerates sector shows that a unit increase in the leverage level will lead to a 0.000810 increase in audit delay. Again, the result has no statistical influence. On a general level it can be seen that leverage and firm size all have negative signs as reflected in the case of industrial goods sector. However, unlike the case of industrial goods firms' firm size has statistical significance value.

Column four shows the result with respect to the banking sector. When corporate governance is not being considered, the result shows a coefficient value of 4.437 which has statistical significance. When variable like firm size is considered, the result shows that a percentage change in firm size leads to a decrease of 0.00343 in audit delay. The result has no statistical significance at 5%. Also, considering the variable like earnings per share, the result shows that

a unit increase in the value of profitability will lead to a 0.000283 decrease in the number of days audit report is delayed. The result also has no statistical significance. Lastly for the banks, the result with respect to leverage shows that a unit increase in the value of leverage will lead to a 0.00326 decrease in the numbers of days financial reports are delayed. The result has statistical significance at 1% and 5% respectively. The general result in the banking sector, only leverage has statistically significant effect.

Column 5 of table 4.2 shows the result with respect to the consumer goods sector. The result shows that in the absence of the firm attributes, audit report of the firms is delayed at a constant rate of 4.737 with statistical significance. The result also shows that a percentage change in the value of firm size will result in a 0.0455 increase in audit delay of the consumer goods sector. The result has statistical significance at 1% and 5% respectively. The result also shows that a unit increase in the value of profitability will result in a 0.00413 decrease in audit delay since the coefficient of profitability is negative. The result is statistically significant at 1% and 5% respectively. With respect to firm leverage, the result shows that the value of coefficient is -0.113 which implies a statistical significant effect. On the overall result for the consumer goods sector two of the variables which are profitability and leverage have negative and significant effects of audit delay.

Column 6 of table 4.2 shows the result with respect to the agricultural firms. The result shows that in the absence of the firm attributes, audit report of the firms is delayed at a constant rate of 4.381 with statistical significance. The result also shows that a percentage change in the value of firm size will result in a 0.0109 increase in audit delay of the consumer goods sector. The result has no statistical significance. Also, the result shows that a unit increase in the value of profitability will result in a 0.000136 increase in audit delay since the coefficient of profitability is positive. The result is however, not statistically significant at 1% and 5% respectively. With respect to firm leverage, the result shows that a unit increase in leverage will lead to a 0.0179 increase in audit delay with statistical significance at 5%.

Column 7 of table 4.2 shows the result with respect to the oil and gas sector. The result shows that in the absence of the firm attributes, audit report of the firms is delayed at a constant rate of 5.450 with statistical significance. The result also shows that a percentage change in the value of firm size will lead to a 0.0907 decrease in audit delay of the consumer goods sector. The result has statistical significance at 1% and 5% respectively. The result also shows that a unit increase in the value of profitability will lead to a 0.00120 decrease in audit delay since the coefficient is negative. The result is statistically significant at 1%

and 5% respectively. With respect to firm leverage, the result shows that the value of coefficient is -0.0192 with a statistical significant effect at 1% and 5%. On the overall result, it shows that all the variables with respect to the oil sector has significant and negative effects.

Column 8 on table 4.2 shows the result with respect to the how firm's attributes affects audit delay of insurance firms listed in the Nigeria stock exchange. The result indicates that when the attributes are not being considered the rate of the delay is at a constant value of 3.671. However, taking into consideration firm size, the result shows that, a percentage change in firm size will lead to a 0.0943 increase in audit delay. The result with respect to firm size has statistical significance at 1% and 10% respectively. In terms of profitability, the result shows that a unit increase in the profit level will result in a 0.000859 increase in audit delay with statistical significance at 5%. On the other hand, taking leverage into consideration, the result shows that a unit increase in the value of leverage will lead to a 0.0158 decrease in audit delay with without statistical significance. The results thus implies that firm size and profitability increases audit delay of insurance firms with statistical significance will leverage decreases the delay, however, without statistical significance.

For the overall result with respect to firm's attributes, the result shows that when the attributes are not in focus, the rate of growth is at a constant value of 4.639. This value has statistical significance at both 1% and 5% respectively. When firm size is taking into consideration, the result shows that the value of the coefficient is -0.0112 which signifies a negative effect. Thus, firm size decreases audit delay but without statistical significance. Also, as profitability is increased by a unit, it will lead to a 0.000611 drop in the delay of financial report. The result with respect to profitability is significant at 1% and 5% respectively. Finally, a unit increase in the value of leverage will result in a 0.000243 increase in the delay of financial reports. Again, the result has statistical significance.

For the discussion with respect to firm attributes and how they determine audit financial reporting timeliness; the result shows that on aggregate level the attributes have significant effect in determining audit delay of the firms. On a specific not, for sectors like: industrial goods, conglomerate, banks and oil and gas, size of the firm has negative relationship with audit delay; this confirm the finding of Mazkiyani and Handoyo (2017). However, only that of conglomerate and oil and gas sectors have significant effect. With respect to the combined sectors the coefficient is negative but not significant. The apriori expectation is that as the size of the firms increases it should cause them to delay their reports. This expectation is only true for conglomerate, agricultural and insurance

sectors. The argument that can support the reduction in delay found in some of the firms is that the firms increase in size along efficiency.

The outcome with respect to profitability shows that increase in profitability reduces delay in financial reporting of industrial goods firms, conglomerate, consumer goods and oil and gas, and the combined sectors. However, only the negative result from the conglomerate, oil and gas and the overall sectors has statistical significance. For these firms being profitable is a sign that the firms are doing well in management. A good management will equally prepare financial reports on time for it to be audited. The opposite is the case of the firms that increasing profitability results in delayed reporting. The finding is supported by the work of Mazkiyani and Handoyo (2017).

For leverage most of the sectors showed an evidence of increasing delay in financial reporting with an increase in the leverage level. Fagbemi and Uadiale (2011) also found similar result. This can be explained in the sense that increasing leverage can signal the fact that the firm is not able to address its finances internally thus has to seek for funding outside. This result also shows evidence of how poor management can affect audit delay of the affected firms. However, for the firms in the consumer goods sector and the oil and gas sector, increasing leverage leads to decrease in financial reporting delay. The argument in support of this position is that leveraged firms tend to be placed under intense monitoring by the lenders. Thus firms would be found to prepare their financial reports, and report it on time to the satisfaction of the lenders. On the overall, the position is that firm attributes determine audit financial reporting timeliness.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

The general result has indicated that most of the firms attributes improves reporting timeliness of all the sectors combined. The result therefore leads to the conclusion that most of the firms attributes in the study reduce audit delay. However, just like the case of corporate governance variables, the effects of the variables varies with each of the sector with some having similar results. Taking the industrial goods sector firm size and profitability reduces audit delay though without statistical significance. The conclusion to this respect is that though growing industrial goods report their financial reports timely, the timeliness is not reasonable. Since the sector is a growing one, the conclusion is that attention should be given to reporting effectively. For the conglomerate sector, they grow with significant level of timely financial reporting while their profit making is not significantly encouraging timely financial reporting. The level of debt of the firm will lead to financial reporting delay as firms tries to balance their debt profile in the financial report. For the

banking sector, the variables perform poorly as the result for firm size and profitability do not have significant consequence even with the negative coefficient of firm size. However, leverage result in increase in reporting delay. The conclusion to this respect is that the variables for firm attributes have not reasonably encourage timeliness of financial report in the banking sector. For the consumer goods and oil and gas firms the result indicated that profitability and leverage all reduced the number of days it takes for financial reports to be filed. This leads to the conclusion that the sector is after sustained growth, by making profit they will report it timely as it sends signals to investors to pick interest in their firms and increasing level of leverage will require evidence of its good utilization (profitability). Thus, firms will want to report timely to show to the lenders or investors that the debt are being put to proper use.

Based on the finding, the study recommends that as firms grow in size the need to have automated system of preparing financial reports becomes eminent. This will do away with size effect were it will take longer time for large firms to prepare their financial reports due to many branches and complicated business dealings. Thus, though the aggregate firm's result shows a decreasing reporting delay with increase in size, the SEC should be mindful of the other sectors these (Firms in the Agricultural, conglomerate and insurance sectors) were increasing size increases delay. It is also recommended that non-profitable and leveraged firms should still try to present their financial reports timely since some investors also takes into consideration future profit prospects and not just the current profit in other to invest in a firm.

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